

Toupet Fundoplication for a Strangulated Hiatal Hernia: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT: Hiatal hernia is a common anatomical abnormality that involves the herniation of abdominal contents through the esophageal hiatus into the mediastinum. It is often asymptomatic, but may present with symptoms of gastroesophageal reflux or life-threatening complications such as strangulation. The treatment is mainly based on a surgical hiatal hernia repair via partial (Toupet) or complete (Nissen) fundoplication. This case report presents a 94-year-old male patient admitted in critical condition due to a strangulated hiatal hernia, and underwent an emergency surgical intervention by performing a partial 180° posterior Toupet fundoplication.

KEYWORDS: Hiatal Hernia; Strangulation; Toupet fundoplication; Laparotomy fundoplication.

INTRODUCTION

Hiatal hernia refers to the herniation of abdominal cavity elements through the diaphragm's esophageal hiatus and into the mediastinum [1]. The vast majority are asymptomatic; however, a minority of individuals may present with symptoms of gastroesophageal reflux disease [2]. Toupet fundoplication is a commonly performed surgical technique for hiatal hernia repair and can also be used in complicated cases such as strangulation.

Here, we present a case of a strangulated hiatal hernia repaired with a partial, 180° posterior fundoplication following the Toupet procedure.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 94-year-old patient, was received a month ago at the emergency room unconscious, and was directly admitted at the intensive care unit with a Glasgow score of 11/15, hypertension, tachycardia, polypnea and urinary retention. An interview was carried out with the patient's relatives in order to obtain further information: the patient had a history of hypertension for 30 years, an unknown cardiopathy for 8 years on aspirin. He was also operated for a left inguinal hernia 25 years ago. In addition, the patient has been diagnosed with type 2 diabetes discovered a week prior to his admission, currently on oral antidiabetic medication, and has been treated during the same period for a urinary tract infection for which he was receiving 2 grams of ceftriaxone per day. However, he stopped taking his aspirin.

The clinical examination was poor, given the patient's altered neurological state. Consequently, the abdominal examination was unremarkable, except for a left inguinal scar related to the repair of his previous hernia.

A cerebral and thoraco-abdomino-pelvic CT scan was indicated. It showed at the cerebral level a subacute ischemic stroke of the superficial territories of the two middle cerebral arteries. The thoracic level of the CT scan revealed a strangulated diaphragmatic hernia (Fig.1) with collapsed surrounding lung parenchyma as well as bilateral pneumopathy of probable infectious etiology, and the abdomino-pelvic level shows minimal hydronephrosis and a supravescical collection around 60x44mm, with a possible communication with the bladder.

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Fig. 1: Thoracic level of the patient's CT scan revealing the strangulated diaphragmatic hernia (arrow).

Thus, based on these findings, the diagnosis of a strangulated diaphragmatic hernia was confirmed, and the indication for an emergency surgery was established. Therefore, the patient was rushed to the operating room.

A pre-operative biological check-up revealed white blood cell (WBC) : $19.42 \times 10^3/\text{ml}$, hemoglobin : 11.6 g/dl, platelets count : $276 \times 10^3/\text{ml}$, and CRP at 258,92 mg/l. The kidney function was severely altered with urea reaching 2.81 g/l, and creatinine 65.90 mg/l. Other blood investigations included HbA1c at 7%, as well as an elevated uric acid with 118.7 mg/l.

Given the patient's unstable condition, intraoperative administration of noradrenaline was necessary. A laparotomic diaphragmatic hernia repair was performed, according to the Toupet technique. Firstly, a median incision was made in order to access the diaphragm. Surgical exploration reveals no peritoneal effusion or signs of digestive ischemia. We proceed to reintroduce hernial contents intra-abdominally, and resect the hernia sac. After that, the cure of the hiatal hernia consists in suturing the diaphragm's pillars with simple separate stitches using 2 silk. Further, the abdominal esophagus has been dissected, and the vagus nerves have been seen and respected. Finally, a 180° posterior fundoplication is performed using the Toupet technique, as well as a gastropexy to left anterolateral abdominal wall (Fig.2). The procedure is completed by draining the thorax with a Joly drain, and the lower mediastinum with an aspirating Redon drain.

Fig.2: Intraoperative image of our patient after a 180° posterior fundoplication of Toupet.

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The rest of the surgical exploration revealed a 30 ml collection of pus (sampled and evacuated) adjacent to the bladder, which was the site of a 1 cm parietal breach. This breach was sutured with separate stitches using 2/0 Vicryl, and a pelvic drainage was set up. Unfortunately, due to delayed post-anaesthetic recovery of consciousness, the patient was taken intubated to the intensive care unit, and declared deceased 3 hours post-operatively from a cardiovascular arrest due to septic shock.

DISCUSSION

Hiatal hernia is a common condition that may or may not present with symptoms of gastroesophageal reflux disease [3], it can also be associated with chest pain, abdominal pain, or respiratory distress [4].

Hiatal hernias are generally classified into four types based on their mechanism and contents within the hiatal hernias :

- Type I (sliding hiatal hernias) are by far the most common, accounting for 85-95% of all cases. It occurs when dilation of the diaphragmatic hiatus allows the stomach cardia and gastroesophageal junction to herniate upward.
- Type II hiatal hernias (paraesophageal hernias) arises from a defect in the phrenoesophageal membrane. The gastroesophageal junction stays in place, anchored to the preaortic fascia, but the stomach herniates adjacent to the esophagus. This type represents approximately 5–10% of all hiatal hernia cases and can be associated with significant morbidity and mortality. It can be complicated by volvulus, strangulation, necrosis (particularly the stomach), bleeding, and obstruction. All symptomatic and any complicated paraesophageal hiatal hernias should be surgically repaired. Surgery improves quality of life and mortality rates, and recurrences are rare.
- Type III hernias broadly have a mixed mechanism and involve components of type I and type II hernias.
- Type IV refers to hiatal hernias that include organs other than the stomach (colon, omentum, or small bowel) within the hernia sac.

Over 90 % of giant hiatal hernias are type III, and herniation of extra-gastric contents is not uncommon. [2], [3], [4], [5].

On chest radiographs, a gas-filled viscus in the lower chest or upper abdomen can lead to the diagnosis of a paraesophageal hernia. Currently, upper endoscopy is the most sensitive and specific diagnostic tool. CT findings make the diagnosis clear and can be very important in establishing the diagnosis when a clinician is aware of the severity of the presentation [5].

Surgery remains the most effective treatment for hiatal hernias, and emergency intervention is essential in cases of strangulation. The most commonly performed procedures for a hiatal hernia repair are partial (Toupet) or complete (Nissen) fundoplication.[3].

The debate between laparoscopic and open surgery has been settled: randomized studies and meta-analyses show that laparoscopic fundoplication is preferred. It offers comparable efficacy, lower mortality (0.04 % vs. 0.2 %), and better cosmetic outcomes Unlike in our case, mesh reinforcement is now standard practice for hiatal hernia repair, as described in numerous studies [6]. Moreover, advances in surgical techniques enabled the increase of robotic-assisted hiatal hernia repairs [4].

CONCLUSION

Hiatal hernia is a disease that should be correctly managed in order to avoid life-threatening complications, such as the strangulation. Surgical intervention is the cornerstone of treatment for symptomatic or complicated cases, with partial (Toupet) and complete (Nissen) fundoplication being the gold-standard repairs. The case of our patient, diagnosed by CT imaging, highlights the importance of the early diagnosis and surgical treatment, especially in vulnerable populations.

REFERENCES

- 1) P. J. Kahrilas, H. C. Kim, et J. E. Pandolfino, « Approaches to the diagnosis and grading of hiatal hernia », *Best Pract. Res. Clin. Gastroenterol.*, vol. 22, n° 4, p. 601-616, août 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.bpg.2007.12.007.
- 2) A. Karan, H. J. Guo, K. Ng, et C. Izzo, « A Breathtaking Hernia: A Giant Hiatal Hernia Masquerading as Poorly Controlled Asthma », *Cureus*, févr. 2022, doi: 10.7759/cureus.22268.
- 3) C. T. Huerta, M. Plymale, P. Barrett, D. L. Davenport, et J. S. Roth, « Long-term efficacy of laparoscopic Nissen versus Toupet fundoplication for the management of types III and IV hiatal hernias », *Surg. Endosc.*, vol. 33, n° 9, p. 2895-2900, sept. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s00464-018-6589-y.
- 4) R. Hoff et B. Qazi, « Strangulated Paraesophageal Hiatal Hernia », *J. Osteopath. Med.*, vol. 118, n° 3, p. 207-207, mars 2018, doi: 10.7556/jaoa.2018.042.
- 5) J. Á. Díez-Ares, N. Peris-Tomás, N. Estellés-Vidagany, et D. Perriñez-Gómez, « Gastric necrosis secondary to strangulated giant paraesophagic hiatal hernia ».
- 6) R. Muramatsu, T. Nobuoka, T. Ito, T. Ogawa, T. Korai, et I. Takemasa, « Laparoscopic mesh repair and Toupet fundoplication for paraesophageal hernia complicated by sliding hiatal hernia: A case report », *Int. J. Surg. Case Rep.*, vol. 100, p. 107664, nov. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.ijscr.2022.107664.